

China's New Cultural Entrepreneurs and Creative Industries, 2000–2022: Guest Editors' Introduction

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Abstract

This Special Issue aims to open new windows on cultural entrepreneurship in China's new media and creative industries from circa 2000 to 2022. It presents four studies on Chinese cultural entrepreneurship in literary production, visual arts, social media, and cinema. These studies analyse from various angles the rise of cultural entrepreneurship – straddling commerce and culture – in China's official and vernacular cultures, including the role of gender and the rise of women cultural entrepreneurs in China's new mediasphere, within an adverse socio-political environment. Analysis of voices, themes, and a network of negotiations and exchanges in literary texts, visual artworks, movies, social media, and the socio-cultural and political discourses in China's mediasphere sheds new light on self-fashioning in transmedia narratives, the new cultural dynamics of the digital age, and the tensions between China's vernacular cultures – which thrive in digital spaces and non-official communities – and the officially ordained culture of the party-state.

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Keywords

Chinese literature, Chinese visual arts, Chinese media, Chinese cultural studies

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Introduction

This special section aims to analyse the role of the new media and creative industries in contemporary China, focusing on the figure of the cultural entrepreneur to open new windows on the cultural flows between such entrepreneurs and the creation of new social tastes and values. This section brings together four contributions by six international scholars of Chinese culture, society, literature, and intellectual history to examine from various perspectives both well-established and emerging examples of cultural entrepreneurship in the fields of literary creation and publication, traditional and online broadcasting, cinema, and social media.

In Chinese mainstream discourse the term “cultural entrepreneur” (文化企业家, *wenhua qiyejia*) – already observed in the late 1990s (Xu, 1997: 28–30) – has become current in recent years to denote the founders and top executives of companies in the creative industries, and, more generally, individuals involved in the commercialisation of cultural products (Liu, 2016: 112–114). Adopting the term in official discourse, the newspaper *Guangming Daily* recently used it to describe the individuals it has selected and celebrated annually since 2012 as the top “personalities of the Chinese creative industries” (*Guangming Daily*, 2012). The list usually includes major figures in private and state-owned companies involved in film production, gaming, online literature, and theatre, among others (*Guangming Daily*, 2012). The compilation of this list, carried out under the auspices of the party’s Propaganda Department, reflects the transformation of how the politico-cultural establishment views individuals who aim at extracting maximum market value from culture. It also sheds light on a policy of control and co-optation vis-à-vis private-sector creative industry entrepreneurs (Ministry of Culture, 2017).

The timeframe under investigation is the early twenty-first century. These four studies specifically cover the period from 2000 to 2022, covering the last years of the Jiang Zemin era (1993–2003) and the rules of Hu Jintao (2003–2013) and Xi Jinping (2013–present). Besides representing the main timespan of the research in this special issue, these dates roughly correspond to two trends in contemporary Chinese media politics. The first marks the beginning of the popularisation of Internet usage in China and the consequent weakening of traditional media gatekeepers, which allowed for the rise of new modes and venues of public expression and cultural entrepreneurialism, such as blogging and online literature (Hockx, 2015; Strafella and Berg, 2016). The closing date corresponds to a trend that is still ongoing and open to interpretation, namely, the relative decline in the party-state promotion of the role of “individual, creative self-expression and grassroots energy” (Wang, 2016: 59) in Chinese society since around 2020–2021.

The articles in this issue note, for instance, that in 2020 the *Guangming Daily* began honouring key companies, rather than individuals, in the creative industries (see our article in this issue) and that the years 2019–2020 witnessed the eclipse of Chen Guo’s star (see Marco Fumian’s article). This trend followed a tightening of the party’s control on cultural affairs in 2018–2019 (Tsai et al., 2023: 59) and paralleled a heightening of its control on media in Hong Kong since 2020 (Lee and Chan, 2023). However, it

is too early to say whether this will mark a turning point in the development of (cultural) entrepreneurship and the creative industries in Xi Jinping's China.

The cultural sphere of early twenty-first century China displays a high degree of interaction and integration between realms such as literary creation, cinema and gaming, artistic production and social media, traditional news media, online citizen journalism, and so on. At the same time, the economic reforms initiated by Deng Xiaoping, and especially since the 1990s, have allowed for the (re)emergence of the figure of the cultural entrepreneur. This figure – who straddles the business world and the cultural field – has often embodied the above-mentioned interaction between different realms of the cultural sphere. Nowadays such interaction and integration centre around the Internet and online creativity – for example, the adaptation of online fiction into films and games.

Furthermore, this special section also examines the role of gender and the emergence of women cultural entrepreneurs in the new mediasphere. As a recent study by Wang and Keane has shown, women entrepreneurs in China's digital creative industries have faced a broad range of challenges in a male-dominated arena (Wang and Keane, 2020). Women entrepreneurs in the digital realm must demonstrate exceptional capabilities to gain visibility – a marginalisation also documented in international studies of female entrepreneurship (Gill, 2018; Oakley, 2013). Breaking new ground at “the crossroads of digital technologies, creativity and commerce,” such women digital creative entrepreneurs appear as “pioneers” (Wang and Keane, 2020: 418).

The four studies in this special section all look at how cultural entrepreneurs in China emerge and establish themselves within a frequently adverse socio-political environment. In the Chinese cultural and media industries, party-state institutions and the official gatekeepers of the cultural scene still play a major role, especially when it comes to business success. Understanding how Chinese cultural entrepreneurs navigate between market demand, party-state supervision, and global cultural flows can shed light on both the present and the future of China's cultural as well as socio-political conditions.

The rise of cultural entrepreneurs in contemporary China represents a by-product of the re-introduction of market principles into the socio-cultural sphere in the Reform Era, especially during the early 1990s (Kong, 2004; Zhu and Nakajima, 2010). If market-oriented reforms since the 1990s sowed the seeds of an entrepreneurial “creative class” (Florida, 2011) in mainland China, the party's emphasis on home-grown “innovation” since the Eleventh Five-Year Plan (2006) has spurred its growth (Keane, 2013: 97–124). In a context where a party-controlled framework tries to function within an imperfect market environment, the dominance of said framework is “challenged by creative entrepreneurs empowered by powerful consumers demanding creative content without state interference” (Chang, 2009: 264). As Chinese authorities seek to develop the national creative industries into a “pillar sector” of the economy with a global influence, they also demand that they deliver “social benefits” and promote “core socialist values” (Ministry of Culture, 2017).

Much of the research on China's creative industries has focused on relevant policies such as the intellectual property regime (Montgomery, 2010) and investment in creative clusters (Keane, 2009) while also examining the development of the art market and the

design industry (Keane, 2013). Several studies on the creative industries in China privilege a geographical dimension, examining creative clusters in cities such as Shanghai (White and Xu, 2012; Zhong, 2016). Keane's (2013) study on China's creative industries points at the clash "between political culture and commercial creativity" and the hope, cherished by "policy makers, academics and even many ordinary citizens," that China will become a "'creative nation' rather than a producer of cheap imitative products" (Keane, 2013: 4). Lily Chumley's study on art schools in China has highlighted the field of tension between the global commodity culture, the nationalistic utopia of China as a cultural superpower, and the cultural creator's pursuit of aesthetic values that transcend the market (Chumley, 2016). The relation between the formation of "taste" and market-oriented creative industries is central to Yi Zheng's study of print media in post-socialist China (Zheng, 2014). Zheng's work draws on theories of class culture and gentility (Berg and Starr, 2007) to investigate how commodities produced by the creative industries contribute to reintroducing taste and class in contemporary China.

Finally, research on cultural entrepreneurship in this special section links up with the growing research on celebrity culture in China. Such research shows how the perception of celebrity in China combines elements such as moral virtue, affluent lifestyle, consumerism, and perseverance (Edwards and Jeffreys, 2010). A consumer culture that emphasises advertising and entertainment defines celebrity in China today, as does a complex interaction between its status and official discourses (Jeffreys and Edwards, 2010; Strafella and Berg, 2015). China today creates "celebrities who 'sell' both products and inspiration to a new generation of aspiring young people and future (world) leaders" (Jeffreys, 2012: 26). Research on celebrity philanthropy and activism also suggests that it could become a "force for social change in China, given the limited spaces available for broader political participation in that country" (Jeffreys, 2016: 773). At the same time, the celebrity industry "operates within an interlinked commercial, technological, legal and political structure, with official discourses embedding celebrity culture in broader narratives around patriotism, progress, and stability" (Sullivan and Kehoe, 2019: 245).

The four papers in this special section examine the rise and spectacle of cultural entrepreneurship in early twenty-first century China's new mediascape from various perspectives.

First, "Author, Artist, Actress: China's New Women Cultural Entrepreneurs" by Berg and Strafella examines the resurgence of cultural entrepreneurship in mainland China by focusing on how digital media have contributed to the rise of a new social phenomenon – women cultural entrepreneurs – while challenging gender roles. After conceptualising the cultural entrepreneur as someone who adds to the "menu" of beliefs and cultural preferences from which culture consumers choose (Currid, 2007; Mokyry, 2013), this study discusses cultural entrepreneurship by Chinese women against the backdrop of the post-reform history of Chinese women entrepreneurs and the growing political importance of the creative industries.

As the Sinophone mediasphere becomes increasingly diversified, market-oriented and celebrity-centred, cultural entrepreneurs invent themselves as "consumption celebrities"

in Guy Debord's sense of the word (Debord, 1992: 39) – their personae epitomising the many facets of consumer culture. The article focuses on Internet author and print novelist Anni Baobei 安妮宝贝 (b. 1974), academic and media personality Yu Dan 于丹 (b. 1965) and online celebrity Papi Jiang (Papi 酱, b. 1987) to analyse how they employ both traditional and new media as platforms for content dissemination while weaving “transmedia” narratives (Jenkins, 2006: 96) about themselves. By doing so, this study shows first, how China's new women cultural entrepreneurs fashion themselves as a new type of celebrity, and second, how their works create a media spectacle.

This media spectacle exists on three levels: first, as the public spectacle of female self-fashioning, casting the new woman cultural entrepreneur as a media celebrity; second, as a multi-media reflection on China's economic reforms and globalisation; and third, as the epitome of the social rise of China's new cultural entrepreneurs. The article thus aims to contribute to our understanding of the cultural and social negotiations surrounding the rise of the new women cultural entrepreneurs in China's mediasphere.

Second, “The Rise of a ‘Fudan Goddess’: Cultural Entrepreneurship in China between Moral Education and Popular Culture” by Marco Fumian investigates the trajectory of Chen Guo 陈果 (b. 1981), a successful cultural entrepreneur who became an Internet celebrity and bestselling author of self-help books thanks to the originality of her teaching methods. Before becoming a commercial cultural producer, Chen Guo was primarily a lecturer at the College of Marxist Studies of Fudan University, where since 2008 she has been teaching a course on “moral-ideological cultivation and legal foundations” (思想道德修养与法律基础, *sixiang daode xiuyang yu falü jichu*). The course represents a pillar of moral education in Chinese higher education, intended to improve the social consciousness of the students in accordance with the ideological principles of the state.

How did Chen Guo create her personal brand of teaching? How did she come to combine her double role as a state ideological educator and a producer of commercial popular culture? What kind of teaching and what kind of values does she promote? Are these values and methods of teaching similar or different in the two different areas of cultural production in which she excels? Such themes are explored in this article. Fumian's article reveals that Chen Guo's teachings, rather than being at odds with each other, are to a very large extent unified, as she has managed to create a moralising but depoliticised approach to teaching which encourages personal self-improvement and social awareness by drawing from the principles and practices of self-help literature – an approach that is therefore suitable for both forms of teaching. For this reason, in March 2019, she was invited to the first national conference of teachers of politico-ideological education presided over by Xi Jinping in Beijing, where she was elevated to the status of national model teacher.

Chen Guo's career and work thus offer a unique case to investigate the interactions and the intersections between official and popular culture in contemporary China, in particular, by observing how the current party-state's ideological apparatuses incorporate the creative use of popular cultural forms in their message with the aim of enhancing the efficacy of the official ideological education.

Third, “Centenarian Memoirs and Vernacular History” by Yi Zheng and Stephanie H. Donald extends the idea of a popular historiography and the question of its emergence in fin-de-siècle China to explore the role of centenary memoirs in the formation of a post-reform vernacular history (Bodnar, 1994: 13–14). The argument of this article posits that these memoirs are a genre and segment of the creative industries that have been commercially successful through directly addressing the problem of history and self-narrative in the People’s Republic of China. The article further examines the transformation of these memoirs from vestiges of state-cultivated intellectual confessions (Sorace, 2018) to vernacular cultural memories (Chen, 2001) that are simultaneously successful in the literary marketplace. Chen Sihe’s conception of the vernacular, which emphasises its intersection with and parallel development vis-à-vis the political institutional and the intellectual elite (Chen, 2001: 112–194), will be used in the discussion for its augmentation of Bodnar’s opposing bifurcation of the official and unofficial, and its historiographical implications for the contention of a contemporary Chinese collective memory.

The popular historiography emerging from these trans-generational memory “fevers” reveals vanishing modern Chinese intellectual values and judgments percolating through the vernacular culture and the associated creative industries of the twenty-first century. The study focuses on creative entrepreneurs in this genre, celebrated centenary memoir writers, centring on Yang Jiang 杨绛 (1911–2016) in juxtaposition with a few others such as Ba Jin 巴金 (1904–2005) and Zhou Youguang 周有光 (1906–2017). The article suggests that the vernacular has been and is the contemporary locus for contesting and retaining politically and socially critical intellectual traditions, while doing so within an openly accessible and commercially viable format.

Fourth and finally, “Community Building Through Screen Sharing: Community Screening as Cultural Practice in Postmillennial Hong Kong and Beyond” by Helena Wu sheds light on the links between creative industries, communal ties and public opinion in Hong Kong by investigating community screenings of the film *Ten Years* (omnibus, 2015). On 1 April 2016, *Ten Years*, a Hong Kong indie film, was simultaneously screened in thirty-six locations across the city with the participation of over thirty-four organising partners from students’ groups and district-based concern groups to non-profit organisations. The screening event drew phenomenal crowds in different parts of the city – on campus, in community halls, beneath the flyovers and on some rooftops. It demonstrates an alternate route for cultural traffic with regard to film circulation and reception. This is not the only instance of such a phenomenon in post-millennial Hong Kong.

Community screening in this study is defined as the exhibition of moving images outside of the commercial theatre circuit. It is noteworthy that since the mid-2010s in Hong Kong, community screenings have been a common activity, organised regularly by local non-profit groups not limited to Hong Kong Community Cinema, Kai Fong Pai Dong, CCCD Artspace Green Wave Art and ToHome (House of To Kwa Wan Stories). Characterising these screenings are the flexible use of urban space, interactions with indie filmmakers and local cultural workers, and the emphasis on communal bonding and freedom of expression.

Based on interviews by Wu with indie film workers, selected community groups and venue providers, this study explores the reinvention of “screens,” the (self-)making of urban cultural space through community film screening, and aims to trace an alternative cultural economy in post-millennial Hong Kong that is built on collective viewing experiences. While Donald and Zheng’s study sheds light on the role of the creative industries in the formation of vernacular narratives of the past, Wu’s article illustrates their influence on imaginaries of China’s future that refuse official grand narratives.

By bringing together these four studies centred around cultural entrepreneurship, this special section advances the study of China’s creative industry beyond city-centred or policy-centred analyses to explore the role of cultural producers, marketers, and consumers in shaping worldviews and lifestyles. If the idea of a “creative class” of entrepreneurs might appear at odds with the party-state’s increasingly authoritarian approach towards the media and official ideology under Xi Jinping (Keane and Chen, 2017), the studies in this special section reveal a complex interaction between official and vernacular cultures – including historical memories, future imaginaries, national dreams, and gendered narratives. Alternative spaces for unofficial histories and collective experiences open up at the same time as the party-state ideological system co-opts celebrity culture and seemingly “depoliticised” genres to amplify its message – the vernacular intersecting with the official, the popular with the elite.

Finally, this special section shows that a focus on cultural entrepreneurship exposes the tensions between political directives, policy objectives, and a vibrant market-oriented media environment, thus opening new approaches to the study of cultural production, circulation, and consumption in today’s China. Future research on China’s creative industries may further explore, for instance, the interplay between the new and the traditional media in the success of cultural entrepreneurs, and also in the formation of stardom and fandoms; the role of social media, local communities, and the publishing industry in sustaining vernacular narratives about the past and the future; and the assimilation of pop and celebrity culture into official ideological work.

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